

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

Call for Students

14/08/2024

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D5.1 _ CALL FOR STUDENTS

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Abstract	This deliverable presents a comprehensive report on the call for students initiated under Task 5.1 in WP5 of the ENTREPRENEDU project. It includes an overview of the call's objectives, promotion strategies, application process, evaluation criteria, and results. Individual submission details from each academic partner are highlighted to reflect their contributions.
Keywords	Call for Students, Venture Building Program, Student Selection, Entrepreneurship, WP5, Task 5.1, ENTREPRENEDU

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0.2	05.08.2024	Academic entities Completed their sections	EBAN, UTH, LUISS, CTBG
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1.0	13.08.2024	Final Version	EBAN, FEA UTH, LUISS, CTBG,

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The ENTREPRENEDU Consortium is the following:

Participant number	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI	FEA	IT
2	FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer	DE
3	EUROPEAN BUSINESS ANGELS NETWORK	EBAN	BE
4	CORALLIA	ATHENA/ CORALLIA	GR
5	CLEANTECH BULGARIA	CTBG	BG
6	F6S NETWORK LIMITED	F6S	IE
7	LUISS	LUISS	IT
8	PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS	UTH	GR

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ENTREPRENEDU project is designed to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and practical entrepreneurship by integrating a comprehensive Venture-Building Programme into educational curricula. This deliverable, part of Task 5.1 within Work Package 5 (WP5), documents the processes and outcomes of the call for students, a crucial step in selecting participants for the upcoming validation phase of the Venture Building Programme.

The primary goal of the ENTREPRENEDU project is to develop a scalable and replicable educational model that strengthens entrepreneurial ecosystems across Europe. By promoting the development of new business models and enhancing entrepreneurial skills, the project addresses critical challenges, including knowledge gaps, financial constraints, regional disparities, and scaling-up risks that often hinder the growth of European entrepreneurship.

In this context, the call for students was structured to attract and select a total of 90 students—30 from each partner institution: Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (LUISS) in Italy, the “Aspekti” Vocational Education and Training Centre of Cleantech Bulgaria (CTBG), and the University of Thessaly (UTH) in Greece—who will participate in the validation phase. The selection process was carefully designed to ensure transparency, inclusivity, and fairness, resulting in a diverse cohort of students from various geographic and demographic backgrounds.

Each academic partner managed their call for students independently, tailoring the process to fit their respective academic schedules and institutional requirements. At this stage, LUISS has successfully completed their call, while UTH and CTBG are set to begin their calls in September.

This deliverable provides a detailed account of the results from LUISS's open call for students, including the number of applications received, the diversity of the selected candidates, and the specific contributions made by each academic partner. The selected students will progress to the programme's validation phase, where they will participate in workshops, mentoring sessions, and practical exercises aimed at testing and refining their business ideas.

In addition to LUISS's outcomes, this deliverable incorporates historical data from previous calls conducted by CTBG and UTH, offering a comprehensive view of their methodologies and how they are planning to integrate this in their Open Call for Students. It also outlines the action plans developed by UTH and CTBG, detailing their strategies for launching their

respective open calls in alignment with their internal timelines. Further details can be found in the relevant sections.

This deliverable not only showcases the successful participant selection process already implemented by LUISS but also details the forthcoming plans of UTH and CTBG to achieve the same. It emphasises the importance of real-world applicability in refining the educational syllabus. As each academic partner progresses according to their internal timelines, they will continue to share data from their respective calls, ensuring the report remains consistently updated with the latest results and insights.

In summary, the call for students is a strong foundation for the ENTREPRENEDU project. With one partner, LUISS, already having completed their call and the others poised to follow, the project is well-positioned to equip the Venture Building Programme with a diverse and capable group of students ready to become the next generation of European entrepreneurs.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The ENTREPRENEDU project, funded under the Horizon Europe framework, aims to bridge the gap between academic learning and practical entrepreneurship by embedding a Venture Building Programme within educational institutions across Europe. This initiative addresses key challenges such as knowledge gaps, financial barriers, regional disparities, and the risks associated with scaling up new ventures.

Work Package 5 (WP5) of the ENTREPRENEDU project is dedicated to the development, implementation, and validation of this Venture Building Programme. Task 5.1 specifically focusses on the call for students, an essential step to ensure the selection of a diverse and motivated group of participants who will engage in the programme's validation phase.

This deliverable outlines the objectives, methodology, and outcomes of the call for students implemented by LUISS and the implementation plans designed by UTH and CTBG. It details the application process, eligibility criteria, promotional strategies, and the selection process used by each partner institution. Furthermore, the results section highlights the number of applications received for the Open Call launched by LUISS, the diversity of selected candidates, and their distribution across the participating institutions.

By documenting these processes and outcomes, this report aims to provide insights into the effectiveness of the call for students and its contribution to the ENTREPRENEDU project's goals. Engaging students in this programme is a critical step towards validating the Venture Building Programme and refining its educational syllabus based on practical feedback and real-world applications.

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE CALL FOR STUDENTS

The main objectives of the call for students are:

- To identify and select at least 90 students (30 per educational partner) for the validation phase of the Venture Building Programme.
- To ensure a transparent, inclusive, and fair selection process.
- To engage students from diverse geographic and demographic backgrounds.
- To validate the Venture Building Programme through practical, real-world applications.

3 DETAILS OF THE CALL

The “Aspekti” VET centre of Cleantech Bulgaria (CTBG), Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (LUISS), and the University of Thessaly (UTH) are the 3 academic entities responsible for the call for students as part of the ENTREPRENEDU Project consortium. The following section will provide a brief overview of the details of the calls from the academic entities.

3.1 CALL DESCRIPTION

The calls are aimed at attracting students interested in the world of entrepreneurship and willing to engage in the in-depth course on Venture Building provided in the frame of the ENTREPRENEDU project. Each partner institution (UTH, LUISS, and CTBG) manages their own call, with UTH and CTBG scheduled to initiate theirs in September. Data from previous years' calls that can provide a solid estimate of the number of students expected by UTH and CTBG is included in this report.

- **UTH** Call Description and Summary

The call for UTH is planned for mid-September, in parallel with the registration of students for university modules. The duration will follow the same guidelines and will be available for at least one month. The programme is expected to begin in mid-October and will run concurrently with the entrepreneurship programme. Last academic year diary: <https://www.econ.uth.gr/en/students/academic-diary>. (See *Annex 8. Academic Diary - UTH*).

The programme is available for 4th-year students in all departments of UTH. The deliverables of the modules will be managed by the Department of Economics. Registration for the Entrepreneurship module will be a prerequisite for registration in the Venture Building programme. The call will be published on the [OPEN e-class \(MOOC\)](#) platform and the university's website. Students will submit their registration through an online form. (See *Annex 9. e-Class MOOC - UTH*).

Supporting documents

- First template of the [Call for Students Form](#). (See *Annex 10. Call for Students Form - UTH*.)

- **Luiss** Call Description and Summary

Luiss students were asked to select elective courses for the academic year 2024/2025 during the month of June 2024. Guidelines on registration were provided by the university, as well as information regarding the course contents and organisation. The course is set to start on September 9th.

Enrolment is available for students in the 2nd year of the Master of Science enrolled at Luiss University. Erasmus students at Luiss University can also opt in for the course. The course belongs to the scientific area of innovation and entrepreneurship. Students must enrol by compiling the online form on their own Web self-service system within the time periods provided (June 2024 for the course of the AY 24-25).

Supporting documents

- The university website calls for the compilation of study plans (see *Annex 1 Call and Guide to the Compilation of Study Plans, LUISS*).
- University Website Course Catalogue and the Entrepreneurship and Venture Capital course summary (see *Annexes 2. Page from Course Catalogue-LUISS*; and *3. "Entrepreneurship and Venture Capital" Course Catalogue Summary-LUISS*).
- University Website Course Page (See *Annex 4. University Website Course Page - LUISS*)

- **CTBG** Call Description and Summary

The application process for the students will be active in September, as this is the time that they go back to the university and finalise their agenda for the new academic year. In order to attract more interest to the opportunity, Cleantech Bulgaria, in their role as a VET provider, will join forces with some of the biggest and most innovative universities in order to have a better reach and engage motivated and eager-to-learn students. The delivery of the programme will start in October.

- Call for student [application form](#) (see *Annex 13. Application Form - CTBG*)
- Past [calls for students example](#) (see *Annex 14. Previous experience with calls for students - CTBG*)

3.2 TIMELINE OF THE CALL FOR STUDENTS

In the following section, each academic entity presents the timeline of their call for students, these times have been estimated / confirmed using the entity's policies and past calls.

- **UTH Timeline**
 - Call prepared: 31 August 2024
 - Call Sent: 20 September 2024
 - Reaching out to students with additional information: 20 September 2024
 - Course starting: 14 October 2024

- **Luiss Timeline**
 - Call prepared: May 2024
 - Call Sent: June 2024
 - Reaching out to students with additional information on the course page: September 2024
 - Course starting: 09 September 2024

- **CTBG Timeline**
 - Call prepared: 31 August 2024
 - Call Sent: 12 September 2024
 - Reaching out to students with additional information: 30 September 2024
 - Course starting: 14 October 2024

3.3 PROMOTION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES:

Each of the academic partners independently manages the promotion and dissemination of their respective calls; the ENTREPRENEDU consortium will further support these activities should the need arise. Given the different nature of the academic partners, each partner was or will be promoted through:

- **UTH Dissemination Strategy**
 - University websites and internal communication channels. [Public MOOC platform](#). (See Annex 9. e-Class MOOC - UTH).
 - Social media platforms: <https://www.facebook.com/kinent.uth> and <https://www.linkedin.com/company/kinet-uth> A total social media presence of more than 3,000 people. (LinkedIn: 566, Facebook: 2,500 followers).

UTH main pages: <https://www.facebook.com/uth.gr/> and <https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-thessaly>.

- **Luiss** Dissemination Strategy
 - University websites, student web-based self-service (see *Annexes 4. University Website Course Page - LUISS*; and *5. Study Plan Submission Instructions, LUISS*)
- **CTBG** [Dissemination Strategy](#) (See *Annex 15. Marketing Strategy for the ENTREPRENEDU Call for Students- CTBG*)
 - Social media platforms are managed by each partner.
 - Newsletters and email campaigns targeted at relevant student groups and associations.
 - Major university websites, social media pages, and newsletters

4 APPLICATION AND SELECTION PROCESS:

Each academic partner had its own selection committee consisting of professors, business experts, and institution members. In the following section, we will be diving deeper into the selection process of each academic institution:

4.1 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

To be eligible, applicants needed to:

- UTH Call Description and Summary
 - Be enrolled at UTH.
 - Be enrolled in the Entrepreneurship module.
 - Have a strong interest in entrepreneurship and venture creation.
 - Be available to participate throughout the programme's duration.
 - Knowledge of English-B1 Minimum
- Luiss Call Description and Summary
 - Be enrolled at LUISS.
 - Have a strong interest in entrepreneurship and venture building.

- Be available to participate throughout the programme's duration.
- Have a BA/BS in Management, Finance, Economics, Engineering, or Political Sciences.
- CTBG Call Description and Summary
 - Have a strong interest in entrepreneurship and venture creation.
 - Be available to participate throughout the programme's duration.
 - Knowledge of English-B1 Minimum

4.2 APPLICATION PROCESS

Applicants were required to submit:

- UTH Application Process
 - A completed online application form. <https://forms.office.com/e/RKvHsnky1v>. (See Annex 10. Call for Students form - UTH).
 - A personal statement explaining their motivation and goals for participating
 - Description of their concept, idea, or business plan
 - Complete a barriers and incentives survey.
- Luiss Application Process
 - The course syllabus was made available on the MSc Course Catalogue.
 - Applicants were required to submit their course choice through the Luiss University online student portal (Web Self Service, see Annexes 5. Study plan submission instructions - LUISS; and 6. Web Self Service access page - LUISS), where it was possible for them to select the course among the list of electives in the course catalogue.
 - The deadline to submit the choice was June 2024. No change was allowed after that deadline.
 - Course choices were confirmed in July.
 - Course will start in September.
- CTBG Application Process
 - A completed [application form](#). (See Annex 13. Application Form - CTBG).

- A personal statement explaining their motivation for participating and a description of their concept idea or business plan, if any.

5 RESULTS

This following section will cover the relevant numbers and information regarding the selected candidates for each institution.

5.1 NUMBER OF APPLICATIONS RECEIVED:

Total applications received: 60
applications expected to be received + 150

Applications per educational partner:

- UTH: 60 Applications are expected based [on last year's registrations](#). (See *Annex 12. 2023 registration - UTH*).
- LUISS: 60 students (the course has reached the maximum enrolment. (See *Annex 7. Elective courses that have reached the maximum enrolment—LUISS*).
- Cleantech Bulgaria: 50 applications are expected, with 30 students to be selected.

5.2 SELECTED CANDIDATES - DIVERSITY:

The selected candidates represented a diverse mix of geographic regions and academic disciplines, reflecting the inclusive nature of the call.

- UTH:
 - Gender distribution: approximately . 65% males, 35% females [Last year's statistics](#) in Orange are female applicants. (See *Annex 11: Gender Distribution Participants - UTH*). The imbalance is due to the increased number of male students in the polytechnic schools. UTH has established a gender and anti-discrimination committee.
<https://www.uth.gr/en/life/support/gender-equality-and-anti-discrimination-committee>
 - Geographic distribution: Thessaly, and Central Greece: 95%. There are few ERASMUS cases per year (mean = 3 students/year).

- Academic backgrounds: Economics, Engineering
- LUISS:
 - Gender distribution: Specific course gender distribution is to be calculated as soon as the course starts (pending enrolment of the Erasmus students).
It is important to note that [Luiss University has a Gender Equality Plan \(GEP\)](#), to enhance gender equality.
 - Geographic distribution: Italy and open to students in the Erasmus programme
 - Academic backgrounds: Economics, Finance, and Management

Cleantech Bulgaria:

- Gender distribution: A specific course gender distribution is to be calculated as soon as the course starts. We expect at least 60% of the applicants to be female, with the remaining 40% being male.
- Geographic distribution: Bulgaria and open to Erasmus+ exchange students
- Academic backgrounds: Economics, Engineering, Finance, and Management

6 NEXT STEPS

As we progress into the critical phase of the Entreprenedu project, our immediate focus will be on finalising Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3, which are integral to the Program Validation Phase of the Venture Building Programme. This phase is essential in providing the selected students with the tools and resources they need to refine and validate their business ideas, ensuring these ideas are both innovative and feasible.

In the coming weeks, our efforts will be concentrated on completing the Venture Building Syllabuses and gathering the relevant educational materials. (See *Annex 16. Venture Building Syllabus - EBAN*). These resources will serve as the foundation for a series of carefully designed lessons and workshops, tailored to meet the specific needs of students as they embark on their venture-building journey. Expert mentors, with deep industry experience, will play a crucial role in guiding the students through the complexities of market validation, business model refinement, and prototype development.

Following the successful completion of Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3, the focus will shift towards launching the Venture Building Programme. This next stage will empower students to

transition smoothly from ideation to implementation, armed with the confidence, knowledge, and strategic insights needed to thrive in today's competitive business environment.

The steps outlined above are pivotal to achieving the Entreprenedu project's objectives, ensuring that the next generation of entrepreneurs is well-prepared to navigate the challenges of the modern business landscape.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The Entreprenedu project is progressing as planned, with significant milestones already achieved. LUISS University in Italy has successfully completed its preparations, setting a strong example for the upcoming phases. The other two partners, the University of Thessaly (UTH) in Greece and Clean Tech Bulgaria (CTBG) in Bulgaria, are also on track, with all necessary preparations in place to finalise their deliverables.

The diversity within our consortium, encompassing three distinct educational approaches across different countries, is a key strength of this project. LUISS offers a Master's program, UTH provides a Bachelor's course, and CTBG delivers a Vocational Education and Training (VET) program. This diverse educational landscape allows us to reach a broader spectrum of students, ensuring that our entrepreneurial training is both comprehensive and adaptable to various academic and professional contexts.

Based on the successful completion of LUISS's tasks and the readiness of UTH and CTBG, we are confident that the project will meet its goals. The combination of varied educational formats and the involvement of partners from Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria enriches the program, providing students with a unique and well-rounded entrepreneurial education. The exceptional success of LUISS's Open Call, combined with the positive momentum from last year's data, reinforces our confidence that we are well-positioned to achieve our goals, empowering students across Europe to excel in their entrepreneurial ventures.

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Call and guide to the compilation of study plans - LUISS

LUISS Programs Student Services Tutoring Teaching news News and Events EN

Home / Student Services / Guide to the compilation of study plans

Guide to the compilation of study plans

STUDENT SERVICES

Contact Information

Graduate School LUISS
Viale Romania, 32
00197 Roma
graduate@school@luiss.it

Dear user, for all the issues related to teaching, please refer to the new email address graduate@luiss.it.

Master's degree programs consist of mandatory core courses, which cannot be replaced by other courses, and several elective courses, which must be taken to earn the required credits for graduation. Students are asked to make choices regarding these courses.

University Academic Regulations for each cohort are available at the [following link](#).

To operate these choices, students must select each course and fill out their study plan online using the [Web Self-Service](#) platform, according to the university's deadlines and procedures. These will be communicated through the usual channels.

All core and elective courses offered to every cohort of every degree program are available on the [Course Catalogue](#).

Please note:

- The study plan must always be confirmed. It is not possible to modify the choices made past the deadline.
- The courses syllabi will be available on [Cattedre Online](#) and on the [Course Catalogue](#).
- For each elective course and for some of the "other activities" there is a maximum number of spots available. To ensure participation in a preferred course, it is recommended to promptly operate the choice as soon as possible within the timeframe set and communicated by the Student Office.
- A minimum number of students is necessary for elective courses and for some of the "other activities" to be activated. The Student Office will contact students to make a second choice if the minimum number of students for a course is not reached.

Annex 2. Page from Course Catalogue-LUISS

<https://luiss.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/corsi/2023/10529/insegnamenti/2#2>

Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[EM38] EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES: AI, MACHINE LEARNING, BLOCKCHAIN, IOT, 5G, QUANTUM & EDGE COMPUTING	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	
Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[M462] ENERGY AND CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	
Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[M186] ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VENTURE CAPITAL	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	
Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[SDS] FASHION MANAGEMENT	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	
Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[M459] HEALTHCARE POLICIES IN EUROPE	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	
Tipo insegnamento: [OPZ] - Opzionale	
[EM32] INTERNATIONAL ACCOUNTING STANDARDS	
Anno di offerta 2024/2025	6 CFU
Primo Semestre	

Annex 3. “Entrepreneurship and Venture Capital” Course Catalogue Summary: LUISS

<https://luiss.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/insegnamenti/2024/15784/2021/2/105297?coorte=2023&schemaid=2102> aa 🔍 A⁺

 Year of enrolment 2023/2024

IT EN

[M186] - ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND VENTURE CAPITAL

 SAVE PDF

General information	
Course	STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT
Curriculum	2 year - BUSINESS MODEL INNOVATION (ENGL) - from English orientation
Course type	Master's Degree
Academic year	2024/2025
Year	2
Training activity type	Optional subjects
Scope	To be chosen by the student
Language	INGLESE
CFU	6 CFU
Didactic Activity Type	Lezione
Evaluation	Voto Finale
Teaching period	Fall semester (from 09/09/2024 to 30/11/2024)
Teaching type	Opzionale
Holders	LECHNER CHRISTIAN
Length	48 hours (48 hours Lezione)
Didactic method	Standard
Subject area	SECS-P/08
Location	Roma - Libera Università Internazionale Studi Sociali "Guido Carli" (LUISS)

Annex 4. University Website course Page - LUISS

Entrepreneurship And Venture Capital

Syllabus

Giuseppe, "jose"
D'alessandro

ADJUNCT PROFESSOR

jdalessandro@luiss.it

Christian Lechner

FULL PROFESSOR

lechner@luiss.it

Open in Luiss Learn

PROFESSORS Giuseppe, "jose" D'alessandro / Christian Lechner

COURSE CODE M186

GENERAL
DISCIPLINE
(SSD) SECS-P/08

COURSE YEAR 2

SEMESTER Primo Semestre

PARTITION OF
STUDENTS 0

CREDITS 6

TOTAL
WORKLOAD 150

TOTAL LESSON
HOURS 48

TEACHING
LANGUAGE English

This is a course about entrepreneurial action. It is project-based and requires constant and continuous work to bring an idea for a new venture as far as possible to its realization. This is an entrepreneurship-in-action course and not simply a course about entrepreneurship. It deals with entrepreneurs and the creation and financing of fast-growing firms.

The main part (Entrepreneurship) is about people and the processes related to launching and building new ventures and transforming them into viable, sustainable and valuable enterprises. In addition, this course addresses the questions of entrepreneurship as a different management style and how entrepreneurial firms can be organized to realize substantial growth in the context of liability of smallness and newness.

The secondary part (Venture capital) has the objective to lead the students to understand what financing options startups have, what venture capital is, how it works, how you can structure a deal.

In this course you will immediately apply what you learn. Entrepreneurship is team-based and your team is your destiny. Only together you can make it !

The course belongs to the scientific area of Innovation and Entrepreneurship.

INSTRUCTIONAL GOALS

The course is designed to give an inside into the process of entrepreneurship and project development with an applied approach to new venture creation including product design and development. It also gives an overview of financing options for startups.

The course is intended to the development of skills and knowledge about design and entrepreneurial process by stimulating competences in judging new product development efforts leading potentially to new ventures.

As such the course gives theoretical insights about entrepreneurship as well as its application in practice.

The educational objectives is to understand the differences between entrepreneurship and management in large corporation, to assess the attractiveness and feasibility of an opportunity and to put practically in place the first steps of the customer journey, i.e. validation the problem, solution, customer and testing customer hypotheses. In addition, it gives an overview of the financing process.

This course is theory and project based. The project work is a way to practice entrepreneurial skill and requires substantial effort during the semester. This is not desk-based research but engaging with the real world. It is an integral part of the course:

The way you practice, is the way you play !

 Knowledge and understanding:

Sufficient insight into entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial processes in order to:

- Understand the role and challenges of an entrepreneur
- Understand the difference between established firms and new ventures
- Understand how to evaluate opportunities
- Understand the strategies of new venture management
- Understand the organizational challenges in launching a potentially fast-growing firm
- Understand the financing process

Applying knowledge and understanding:

- Identifying and evaluating opportunities for start-ups
- Perform customer validation
- Developing a business model for start-ups
- Developing entry strategies for new ventures
- Developing requirements for an appropriate new venture team
- Develop a concept for establishing a financing package

 INTENDED
LEARNING
OUTCOMES

Making judgments:

Students will acquire experience in making judgments about business opportunities and their feasibility

Communication skills

- students will develop communication skills for presenting project work

Learning skills

- Dealing with uncertain outcomes, students will learn how to approach and validate their projects

 BA/BS in Management, Finance, Economics, Engineering, Political Sciences

PREREQUISITES

COURSE CONTENTS	<p>What is entrepreneurship?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business ideas • Evaluation of entrepreneurial opportunities • The link between entrepreneurial firm typologies and opportunities • Problem validation, solution validation and value proposition • Entry strategies • Entrepreneurial teams and networking • Resourcing the new venture • The financing process • Venture capital
REFERENCE BOOKS	<p>- Neck, H, Neck, C, and Murray, E., (2018). Entrepreneurship – Mindset and Practice, Sage Publications;</p> <p>- Smith & Smith 2019: Entrepreneurial Finance - Venture Capital, Deal Structure & Valuation, 2nd Edition, Stanford University Press.</p> <p>Additional Articles will be added in due course</p>
TEACHING METHODS	<p>We will be experimenting with Challenge Based Learning, working on a flipped-classroom approach encouraging students to search and to critically review existing knowledge, and at the same time to apply generated learnings.</p> <p>At the core is the team project work. Case studies will be used to explore in more depth certain aspects. We will class discussions, case studies and videos.</p> <p>Attention and learning will be, additionally, stimulated through the use of interactive platforms like Mentimeter.</p>
ASSESSMENT METHOD	<p>Throughout the course, there will be continuous verifications via weekly progress tracking, group assignments and case studies. For the final grade count the project work during the course for 70% and the final written exam, which consists in the final project presentation by the teams for 30%. Class participation is essential and taken for granted</p> <p>There will be no midterm exam.</p>
THESIS ASSIGNMENT CRITERIA	<p>Min 27/30 exam grade</p>
EXTENDED PROGRAM AND REFERENCE READING MATERIAL	
WEEK1 - LESSON 1	<p>Idea Generation, Problem identification</p> <p>Reflection on entrepreneurship: a conceptual evolutionary framework from theory to practice and from a number of different points of view: economical, societal, psychological. Project goals and team building.</p>

WEEK1 - LESSON 2	Exploring entrepreneurial opportunities. The importance of timing for entrepreneurial opportunities
WEEK1 - LESSON 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entrepreneurship as a user centred approach - Entrepreneurship as the scientific method - Problem validation (1)
WEEK1 - LESSON 4	Problem validation & Customer discovery (2)
WEEK1 - LESSON 5	Solution Validation & Solution Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solution validation methods - Working on the problem-solution fit.
WEEK1 - LESSON 6	Crafting the Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Value proposition & competitor analysis - Prototyping & MVP (minimum viable product) - Product-market-fit.
WEEK1 - LESSON 7	Entry Strategies and Market Discovery <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entry strategies - customer segmentation - first clients for startups - analysis of target market - tools for data collection
WEEK1 - LESSON 8	Business Model Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Business Modelling for startups - The entrepreneurial team, networks, mentors and ecosystems
WEEK1 - LESSON 9	Access to Finance and Funding An in-depth look of how venture capital works. Discussion on how to fund growth in every stage both from the entrepreneur and the investors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding mechanisms and criteria of entrepreneurial projects
WEEK1 - LESSON 10	Venture financing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding proposals - Due diligence documents - Term sheets
WEEK1 - LESSON 11	Financial projections & - Funding needs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pitch Deck & Presentation Techniques
WEEK1 - LESSON 12	Pitch-presentations: Theory & Practice

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Annex 5. Study plan submission instructions - LUISS

https://www.luiss.edu/students/student-office/masters-degree-programs/compiling-study-plan

LUISS SOCIAL TV THE UNIVERSITY PROGRAMMES RESEARCH SCHOLARSHIPS APPLY NOW EVENTS

Home / Enrolled Students / Students Services / Student Office / Master's Degree Programs / Compiling a study plan

Compiling a study plan

Study plans can only be **compiled online** through the **Web Self Service** within the time periods provided for your degree program and year of registration. Outside of these periods it will not be possible to make selections or change selections already made.

For students that do not make a selection or do not confirm it within the established deadlines, a departmental study plan will be created, which cannot be changed.

Before accessing the Web Self Service to make your choices, please read the following table, paying attention to your degree program and year of registration:

- [Study Plan A.Y. 2024-2025 - Master's Degree Programs](#)

← Master's Degree Programs

Annex 6. Web Self Service Access Page - LUISS

https://www.luiss.edu/students/web-self-service

LUISS SOCIAL TV THE UNIVERSITY PROGRAMMES RESEARCH SCHOLARSHIPS APPLY NOW EVENTS

Web Self Service

← Enrolled Students

- STUDENTS ENGAGE AND DEVELOPMENT
- STUDENTS SERVICES
- CULTURAL ACTIVITIES
- RESTRICTED AREA
- EXAM WORKOUT
- SHARING MOBILITY
- CAMPUS LIFE
- NOTICES

Using the University's **Web Self Service**, students can access the following **services**:

- view and update their address and contact information
- check the status of payments made or to be made
- view and print self-certification forms
- **view and fill out study plans**
- view their course of studies and list of examinations passed or to be taken
- check available exam dates
- reserve examination dates (up to 5 days before the exam)
- check announcements regarding opportunities to study or perform internships abroad

To access the service, students must enter a user ID (identification number) and password (PIN).

For security purposes, it is recommended that students **properly close each session** after they have finished.

[Access Web Self Service](#)

Annex 7. Elective courses that have reached the maximum enrolment - LUISS

The screenshot shows the LUISS website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Programs, Student Services, Tutoring, Teaching news, and News and Events. Below this, a header section reads "Graduate School elective courses that have reached the maximum number of spots available:". A table follows, listing various courses with their codes, titles, and professors. The course "M186 Entrepreneurship and venture capital" is highlighted with a yellow border, indicating it has reached maximum enrolment. The table also includes other courses like "Language in Advertising", "Economia dei media digitali", "War and Crisis Management", "Machine Learning in Marketing", "Diplomacy and negotiation", "Gestione dei processi commerciali e delle reti di vendita", "Project management", "Geopolitical Scenario and Political Risk", and "International Trade and commercial policies".

Cod. AD	Course	Professor
EM21	Language in Advertising	Peverini Paolo
EM52	Economia dei media digitali	Balestrieri Luca
EM64	War and Crisis Management: the role of Defense in International Relations	Cannizzaro Marcello/Ciocca Paolo
EM66	Machine Learning in Marketing	Laura Luigi
M186	Entrepreneurship and venture capital	Lechner Christian/ D'alessandro Giuseppe
M230	Diplomacy and negotiation	Pasquale Ferrara
M234	Gestione dei processi commerciali e delle reti di vendita	D'ambrosio Daniele
M282	Project management	Nunziata Eugenio
M314	Geopolitical Scenario and Political Risk	Giuseppe Scognamiglio
SJO	International Trade and commercial policies	Manzocchi Stefano

Annex 10. Call for Students Form: UTH

Entreprenedu Venture Building Program Registration form-University of Thessaly

Important note: The registration on the module "Introduction to Entrepreneurship" is prerequisite for enroll in Venture Building Program. More info <https://entreprenedu.eu/>
Σημαντική σημείωση: Η εγγραφή στην ενότητα "Εισαγωγή στην επιχειρηματικότητα" είναι απαραίτητη προϋπόθεση για την εγγραφή στο πρόγραμμα Venture Building.

* Required

1. Name/Όνομα *

2. Surname/Επίθετο *

3. Gender/Φύλο *

Male/Ανδρας

Female/Γυναίκα

Annex 8. Academic Diary - UTH

Home | Department of Economics | Studies | **Students** | News | Research

You are here: / Students / Academic Diary

Details
 28 November 2023 401

Academic Diary 2023 - 2024

Winter Semester:
 Start: **23 October 2023**
 End: **02 February 2024**
 Examinations period: **05 February - 23 February 2024**

Spring Semester:
 Start: **26 February 2024**
 End: **14 June 2024**
 Examinations period: **17 June - 05 July 2024**
 September examinations period: **02/09/24 - 20/09/24**

National and Religious Holidays 2023-2024

Winter Semester
 28 October, *National Holiday*
 17 November, *Schools Holiday*
 18 October, *Regional holiday Lamia (St. Loukas' day)*
 4 December, *Regional holiday Karditsa (St. Serafeim' day)*
 6 December, *Regional holiday (St. Nickolaos' day)*
 23 December 2023 - 5 January 2024, *Christmas Holidays*
 30 January, *Schools Holiday*
 06 January, *Schools Holiday*

Spring Semester
 18 March, *Ash Monday*
 25 March, *National Holiday*
 29 April - 10 May, *Easter Holidays*
 01 May, *National Holiday*
 15 May, *Regional holiday Larissa (St. Achilleios' day)*
 24 June, *Holy Spirit Holiday*

ACADEMIC NEWS | **SECRETARIAT NEWS**

 Closure conference/Seed funding seminar - AGILE4CIRC
 25.01.2022 365

 Call for papers (deadline extended): Economics of knowledge creation and utilization in regions
 02.07.2021 1327

 SCOPE project final conference
 30.09.2019 882

F.A.Q.

UTH Annex 9. e-Class MOOC - UTH

The screenshot shows the login page of the UTH e-Class MOOC. The page is in Greek and features the logo of the University of Thessaly (UTH) on the left. The main content area is titled "Πλατφόρμα Τηλεκπαίδευσης Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας" and "Σύνδεση χρήστη". A yellow warning box states: "Η σελίδα που προσπαθείτε να μπείτε απαιτεί όνομα χρήστη και συνθηματικό. Η πλατφόρμα σας ανακατεύθυνε αυτόματα στην αρχική σελίδα για να συνδεθείτε προτού προχωρήσετε σε άλλες ενέργειες. Πιθανόν, να έληξε η σύνδεσή σας." Below this, there is a "Σύνδεση με eclass" section with input fields for "Όνομα χρήστη (username)" and "Συνθηματικό (password)", a "Είσοδος" button, and a link for "Ξεχάσατε το συνθηματικό σας;". A "Επιστροφή" button is also present. The footer contains the text "Open eClass © 2003-2024 — Όροι Χρήσης — Πολιτική Απορρήτου".

Annex 11. Gender Distribution Participants - UTH

Students 2022-2023

Orange represents female participants.

Annex 13. Application Form - CTBG

Application form - ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Program

jp@eban.org [Switch account](#)

 Not shared

* Indicates required question

Name / Име *

Your answer _____

Surname / Фамилия *

Your answer _____

Gender / Пол *

Female / Жена

Male / Мъж

Prefer not to say / Предпочитам да не отговарям

Annex 12. 2023 Registration - UTH

Αριθμός μητρώου	Όνομα χρήστη (username)	Ημερομηνία εγγραφής
	1616125 KPOLYCHRONIDIS	2023-06-26 00:34:16
0315125	gkylindris	2023-08-01 14:34:05
	1617153 ppetikas	2023-09-05 02:57:52
	1620263 mzafeiris	2023-10-03 02:24:12
02956	cpantazop	2023-10-12 18:14:00
	1520143 tasianas	2023-10-14 15:45:56
	2915 kgiannikoglou	2023-10-16 15:49:47
02987	angkoutsis	2023-10-17 12:30:08
03179	ckaimakami	2023-10-17 22:28:42
	tpetros	2023-10-20 18:04:31
03094	gstampoulidis	2023-10-21 11:57:05
03088	kgerostergios	2023-10-21 11:58:54
03137	vakaraiskou	2023-10-22 10:46:57
02923	gepanagiotidis	2023-10-22 13:28:14
03361	ablatsouka	2023-10-22 22:01:51
02627	atbarka	2023-10-22 22:43:00
02960	dgelantz	2023-10-23 11:19:38
03133	fbekou	2023-10-23 13:16:16
	dgaliotou	2023-10-23 13:48:49
03383	ppolykleitou	2023-10-23 14:19:01
	260510510220 nfytrou	2023-10-23 14:23:10
02818	kokyriaki	2023-10-23 14:27:29
03142	ptisilis	2023-10-23 15:33:09
03004	gtrachilis	2023-10-23 15:37:26
03240	ilanga	2023-10-23 16:16:20
03212	ppapoulias	2023-10-23 16:46:01
03243	atrikaliotis	2023-10-23 17:24:07
03009	achelvatz	2023-10-23 17:43:57
03023	zstylianou	2023-10-23 18:07:40

03242		gespiliopoulos	2023-10-23 18:40:34
	1620222	csianidis	2023-10-23 18:48:09
0220039		evourou	2023-10-23 18:58:58
M011622047		lkafidas	2023-10-23 20:31:09
03128		Kntailianis	2023-10-24 01:43:53
	1120049	aspachi	2023-10-24 14:23:29
03046		ckodonas	2023-10-24 17:51:24
AM323053		vgeorgopoulou	2023-10-25 09:02:00
	1620	pnatsiopoulou	2023-10-25 14:16:36
	3821032	asdiamanti	2023-10-25 15:23:46
03061		ezampras	2023-10-26 11:01:21
03014		ptsatanis	2023-10-26 14:52:19
02945		ckonstantin	2023-10-26 15:55:31
03351		dchadios	2023-10-26 19:48:43
0515004		nalexopoulos	2023-10-26 20:36:34
02831		makonst	2023-10-26 21:21:21
0419192		iokyritsis	2023-10-27 04:01:59
02967		gtzamas	2023-10-27 19:07:16
	239	apapostolidis	2023-10-27 19:38:07
02943		vbantis	2023-10-27 22:03:48
	1619070	iokoufopoulos	2023-10-28 22:02:54
02599		ppapavlachos	2023-10-30 07:35:17
02991		ipateras	2023-10-30 12:50:22
	27080100111	gziopoulos	2023-10-30 16:04:10
05257		nmalliaras	2023-10-30 17:19:16
03405		cblatsioti	2023-10-30 17:34:17
	3821038	chkonstantinidou	2023-10-30 18:10:48
	1620148	mfalia	2023-10-30 19:00:29
	3021	gfilippou	2023-10-30 19:58:09
025779		ntheodoridis	2023-10-30 20:23:29
02918		nimaniatis	2023-10-31 14:31:58

	1620015	konroustas	2023-10-31 23:11:41
	1520021	stassi	2023-11-06 18:27:30
02427		ivrachnos	2023-11-06 18:59:35
00444		dvousvouras	2023-11-06 19:07:40
	1,18701E+15	mgkiliopoulou	2023-11-06 19:52:06
		zapostolos	2023-11-06 20:19:50
	2786	pstavrini	2023-11-07 10:21:10
	3279	amileas	2023-11-07 10:22:49
0951		asgalano	2023-11-08 11:23:44
	1622096	akaravariotis	2023-11-08 16:20:26
04864		cvoulgarakis	2023-11-12 18:58:00
	1621280	dsalich	2023-11-14 11:27:43
	253642824239	mkavrigiannis	2023-11-14 12:34:23
00296		ptachtsidou	2023-11-14 13:24:42
	21049829	kkaratasios	2023-11-16 23:46:15
Ελένη		geornikou	2023-11-18 14:25:12
	3820033	anmatsouka	2023-11-20 17:17:41
	178522585	aterpou	2023-11-21 15:14:45
	3639	npavntegia	2023-11-21 23:13:50
	3337	kkleovoulou	2023-11-25 13:46:44
03599		Pnanousis	2023-11-26 23:40:19
	1621258	konsapostolou	2023-11-27 19:37:17
03432		dgiarlelis	2023-11-28 01:29:15
02333		dgeorgianos	2023-12-03 22:32:26
0219147		emala	2023-12-12 16:49:29
02222		gsiomou	2024-01-04 19:03:07
	1621152	georangeli	2024-01-16 18:11:27
	1613163	ngrigoriou	2024-02-05 09:17:05
	1715	vprovataris	2024-02-06 16:46:56
	2121256	tgogoulas	2024-02-11 12:34:35
04825		iosman	2024-02-14 02:52:01

	1622011 andmargarit	2024-02-26 00:01:36
	2370 plavdi	2024-02-26 00:28:03
04900	dimitrstergiou	2024-05-09 22:56:49
	1616149 mkomini	2024-05-30 18:32:42
	1618232 evioannidi	2024-06-22 12:23:27
03422	ekaklopoulos	2024-07-16 19:19:38
03411	diasvestas	2024-07-20 22:04:44
	1621003 mtsantikou	2024-08-01 19:27:34
04440	maripetridou	2024-08-06 08:12:09

Annex 14. Previous experience with calls for students - CTBG

CLEANTECH BULGARIA'S PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE WITH CALLS FOR STUDENTS FOR EDUCATIONAL INITIATIVES AND PROGRAMS

Cleantech Bulgaria boasts a rich history of successfully launching and managing educational initiatives and programs targeted at university students. With years of experience in fostering innovation and entrepreneurship, we have consistently designed and executed comprehensive calls for participation, attracting a diverse pool of talented students from various academic disciplines. Our expertise spans from conceptualizing program curricula to implementing effective outreach strategies that resonate with the student community. We have a proven track record of collaborating with universities, student associations, and industry experts to create dynamic, hands-on learning experiences that empower students to turn their ideas into impactful ventures. Our commitment to educational excellence and student engagement ensures that each initiative not only meets but exceeds expectations, driving substantial student involvement and success.

EXAMPLE OF A PREVIOUS CAMPAIGN

In 2023, Cleantech Bulgaria (CTBG), in a partnership with the Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology (MCAST), successfully implemented the “Youth for Sustainable Mobility and Inclusion – TRAILS” project financed by EIT Urban Mobility.

TRAILS fostered innovation in electromobility education in Bulgaria and Malta. The objective was to ignite and expand the education and future work capacity in these two countries from the regional innovation scheme. The project began with an assessment of the local needs in electromobility and new vehicle technologies. A specifically developed training methodology for teachers enabled the transfer of knowledge from the Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology and Cleantech Bulgaria to local industry, professional schools and higher education institutions, enabling educators to develop new methodologies to teach skills that are needed for the future of mobility. To address the specific needs of industry partners, the project also included a strong collaboration between local educational institutions and industry partners. **Additionally, in order to test the created methodology, one training per country was organized with university students.**

For this campaign Cleantech Bulgaria partnered up with the University of National and World Economy. The call was announced on 15 Oct 2023 with a deadline of 10 Nov 2023. The used tools were social media campaign, as well as university news article and newsletter. 54 applications were received, resulting in 30 participants being selected for the training.

Annex 15. Marketing Strategy for the ENTREPRENEDU Call for Students - CTBG

MARKETING STRATEGY FOR THE UPCOMING CALL FOR STUDENTS FOR THE ENTREPRENEU VENTURE BUILDING PROGRAM

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To effectively reach and engage university students, encouraging them to apply for the Venture Building Program by highlighting the program's unique features, benefits, and potential for business development.

TARGET AUDIENCE

- Primary audience: University students from various disciplines with an interest in entrepreneurship, innovation, and startup culture.
- Secondary audience: University associations, entrepreneurship clubs, faculty members, and career development centres to further disseminate the opportunity.

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

- Social media
- University websites and newsletters
- Email campaigns
- Student associations and clubs

CONTENT STRATEGY

- **SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN**

Platforms: Facebook, LinkedIn

Module Highlights:

- Post introducing the program
- Posts summarizing each module.
- Using infographics to break down the steps of venture building
- Using infographics showing the journey from “idea generation” to “funding” with icons representing each module.

Student testimonials:

- Showcasing testimonials from the participants of the mentoring ENTREPRENEDU mentoring program

Interactive content:

- Polls/Quizzes on entrepreneurial knowledge or idea generation techniques.

Countdown and deadlines:

- Regular countdown posts leading up to the application deadline.

- **UNIVERSITY WEBSITES AND NEWSLETTERS**

Universities will receive a prepared new article to upload on their websites, as well as to disseminate in their newsletters. The article will include introductory information about the project and the Venture Building program, as well as detailed information about the modules, benefits, deadlines etc.

- **EMAIL CAMPAIGN**

We will disseminate a targeted email campaign among our own database, including all the relevant information about the project and the Venture Building program, as well as detailed information about the modules, benefits, deadlines etc.

- **OUTREACH AND STUDENT ASSOCIATIONS AND CLUBS**

We will reach out to student associations and young entrepreneurship clubs in order to be able to engage more applicants.

IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE

- Week 37:
 - Social media posts; CTBG website update
- Week 38:
 - Initial email campaign;
 - Social media posts to highlight the modules of the program;
 - Student associations outreach
- Week 39:
 - Continued email campaign
 - Continued social media promotion
- Week 40:
 - Final social media countdown
 - Last email campaign
 - Final push through student associations

Annex 16. Venture Building Syllabus - EBAN

Module 0: Venture Building Group Project

Identifying and presenting your problem

Crafting your solution
- Case studies and real-world examples illustrating successful idea generation and validation strategies:

MODULE 1: Problem Identification and Validation, Idea Generation:

UNIT 1: Techniques for innovative idea generation:

- Brainstorming sessions,
- Problem-solving methodologies and Design thinking exercises.

UNIT 2: Validation of identified problems:

- Utilization of tools and frameworks for problem validation, including SWOT analysis and customer journey mapping.
- Techniques for ensuring market fit and demand validation.

UNIT 3: Strategies for identifying market needs and pain points:

- Understanding market research techniques for identifying gaps, needs and opportunities.

MODULE 2: Solution Development and Validation, Crafting Value Proposition:

UNIT 1: Solution validation methods:

- Design thinking tool for exploring and validating solutions
- A/B testing, usability testing, and pilot studies.
- Assess solution viability and market readiness.

UNIT 2: Crafting a unique value proposition:

- Understanding Customer Needs and Differentiation Strategies.
- Utilizing Value Proposition Canvas.
- Presenting Individual Value Propositions.

UNIT 3: Prototyping techniques for MVPs:

- Creating minimum viable products.
- Gathering feedback from users.

MODULE 3: Market Discovery:

UNIT 1: Fundamentals of market research:

Research the market

- Understanding customer segmentation for targeted strategies.
- Analysis of target market for effective positioning.

UNIT 2: Utilization of digital tools:

- Methods for data collection, analysis, and visualization.
- Implementing tools to enhance market insights and decision-making.

UNIT 3: Hands-on projects and case studies:

- Applying market research techniques to real-world scenarios.
- Developing skills through practical exercises and simulations.
- + Guest lectures from industry experts sharing insights and best practices in market research.

MODULE 4: Business Model Development:

UNIT 1: Introduction to Business Model Development:

- Understanding the fundamentals of business models.
- Exploring various types and their applications.

UNIT 2: Methods and Tools for Business Model Development:

- Understanding different methods and tools such as Business Model Canvas (BMC) for Business Model Development.
- Mapping key components such as value proposition and customer segments.

UNIT 3: Resources - Soft skills team building (advantages of diversified team) and mentoring opportunities:

- Building an Effective and Diverse Team:
 - Advantages of diversified teams: Leveraging diverse perspectives for innovative problem-solving. Incorporating
 - Strategies for assembling a strong and diverse team: Identifying complementary skill sets and roles within the team. Techniques for fostering collaboration and trust.
 - Enhancing leadership, teamwork, and presentation skills. Building effective communication channels.
 - Enhancing conflict resolution and decision-making skills.

UNIT 4: Social Responsibility and Sustainable Practices (optional, but relevant):

- Examination of corporate social responsibility (CSR) principles and frameworks for ethical business conduct.
- Integration of sustainability practices into business operations, including environmental conservation, social impact, and ethical supply chain management.

Develop a Business Model with your team
- Analysis of successful business models in different industries.
- Hands-on projects to apply BMC and revenue/cost structures.

- *Evaluation of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria and their implications for business sustainability and stakeholder engagement.*
- *Case studies highlighting successful examples of socially responsible and sustainable businesses.*

MODULE 5: Access to Finance and Funding

UNIT 1: Overview of various funding mechanisms:

- Venture capital, angel investment, crowdfunding, EU funding and government grants.
- Analysis of funding criteria, terms, and conditions for different funding sources.

UNIT 2: Preparation of funding proposals:

- Crafting funding proposals and pitch decks.
- Developing due diligence documents for investor consideration.

UNIT 3: Financial projections and funding needs:

- Developing revenue forecasts, cash flow statements, and break-even analysis.
- Quantifying funding needs based on business objectives and growth plans.

UNIT 4: Crafting compelling investment pitches:

- Techniques for attracting funding from various sources.
- Tailoring pitches for investors, accelerators, and funding agencies.
- Pitch simulation exercises and feedback sessions to refine pitching skills and presentation techniques.
- + Guest speaker sessions: featuring investors, entrepreneurs, and funding experts sharing their experiences and insights. (Case studies, success stories, tips and tricks).

UNIT 5: Exits

- A very brief overview of exits, informing Students on why it is important to keep exits in mind at an early stage of the venture-building process. since some investors might ask some questions or could already activate their contacts to facilitate exits. The research and negotiation process can take a long time and it is ideal to start asap.
-

Prepare for funding and deliver a pitch

Goal of the Module
<p>Objective 2: Competence in Problem Validation</p> <p>Students will acquire skills in utilizing tools and frameworks such as SWOT analysis and customer journey mapping to validate identified problems.</p> <p>Students will understand and employ techniques for ensuring market fit and demand validation to ascertain the viability of their ideas.</p> <p>Objective 3: Strategic Identification of Market Needs and Pain Points</p> <p>Students will develop an understanding of market research techniques necessary for identifying gaps, needs, and opportunities in the market.</p> <p>Students will learn to systematically analyze and interpret market data to identify potential</p>				

Goal of the Module
<p>their solutions are practical and feasible for market introduction.</p> <p>Objective 2: Crafting and Communicating a Unique Value Proposition</p> <p>Students will gain insights into understanding customer needs and differentiating their solutions from competitors through strategic analysis.</p> <p>Students will learn to utilize the Value Proposition Canvas to systematically develop and refine their value propositions.</p> <p>Students will be able to present and articulate individual value propositions clearly and persuasively to stakeholders and potential customers.</p> <p>Objective 3: Mastery of Prototyping Techniques for MVPs</p> <p>Students will acquire skills in creating minimum viable products (MVPs) to test and iterate on their solutions efficiently.</p> <p>Students will learn techniques for gathering and analyzing feedback from users to inform iterative improvements and refinements of their MVPs.</p>				

Goal of the Module
<p>competitive advantage.</p> <p>Objective 2: Proficiency in Utilizing Digital Tools for Market Research</p>				

Objective 2: Proficiency in Utilizing Digital Tools for Market Research

Students will learn methods for data collection, analysis, and visualization to derive actionable market insights.

Students will implement and utilize various digital tools to enhance their market research capabilities and support data-driven decision-making.

Objective 3: Practical Application of Market Research Techniques

Students will apply market research techniques to real-world scenarios through hands-on projects and case studies, bridging theory and practice.

Students will develop and refine their market research skills through practical exercises and simulations, preparing them for real-world challenges.

Objective 4: Exposure to Industry Expertise and Best Practices

Goal of the Module

including their significance and impact on business success.

Students will explore various types of business models and their applications across different industries.

Objective 2: Proficiency in Business Model Development Methods and Tools

Students will learn and apply different methods and tools for business model development, with a focus on the Business Model Canvas (BMC).

Students will develop the ability to map and analyze key components of business models, such as value propositions and customer segments.

Objective 3: Building Effective and Diverse Teams

Students will understand the advantages of diversified teams, including leveraging diverse perspectives for innovative problem-solving and incorporating varied skills for comprehensive project coverage.

Students will learn strategies for assembling strong and diverse teams, identifying complementary skill sets and roles, and fostering collaboration and trust.

Students will enhance their soft skills in leadership, teamwork, presentation, communication, conflict resolution, and decision-making.

Objective 4: Integration of Social Responsibility and Sustainable Practices

Students will examine principles and frameworks of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and ethical business conduct.

Students will learn to integrate sustainability practices into business operations, focusing on environmental conservation, social impact, and ethical supply chain management.

environmental conservation, social impact, and ethical supply chain management.
Students will evaluate Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria and understand their implications for business sustainability and stakeholder engagement.
Students will analyze case studies highlighting successful examples of socially responsible and

Goal of the Module

...

...

...

...

Students will learn how to craft effective funding proposals and pitch decks tailored to different types of investors and funding sources.
Students will develop the skills needed to prepare due diligence documents that meet investor requirements and standards.
Objective 3: Proficiency in Financial Projections and Assessing Funding Needs

Students will acquire skills in developing detailed revenue forecasts, cash flow statements, and break-even analyses to support their funding proposals.
Students will learn how to quantify their funding needs based on their business objectives and growth plans, ensuring accurate and realistic financial planning.
Objective 4: Expertise in Crafting Compelling Investment Pitches

Students will learn techniques for attracting funding from various sources by crafting compelling investment pitches.
Students will understand how to tailor their pitches for different audiences, including investors, accelerators, and funding agencies.
Students will engage in pitch simulation exercises and receive feedback to refine their pitching skills and presentation techniques.
Objective 5: Practical Insights from Industry Experts

Students will benefit from guest speaker sessions featuring investors, entrepreneurs, and funding experts who will share their experiences, insights, and best practices.
Students will analyze case studies and success stories, gaining practical tips and tricks for securing funding and navigating the funding landscape.

MODULE 1
PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION AND VALIDATION, IDEA GENERATION

MODULE CODE	VB6801
MODULE TITLE	Problem Identification and Validation, Idea Generation
PROGRAMME	
DEPARTMENT	
CREDITS	
STAGE OF STUDY	
SEMESTER/SESSION	
LOCATION	
STAFF	
E-MAIL	

DESCRIPTION
<p>This module delves into the critical initial stages of the innovation process, where students will learn to identify significant problems and generate creative solutions. The journey begins with thorough problem identification, emphasising the importance of recognising and articulating issues that are worth addressing. This involves techniques for observing and researching within specific contexts or industries, enabling participants to pinpoint problems that have a real impact.</p> <p>Following problem identification, the module focuses on validation, where students will employ various methods to confirm the significance and relevance of these problems. Techniques such as stakeholder interviews, surveys, and market analysis will be used to gather data and feedback, ensuring that the identified problems are real, urgent and worth solving. Once the problem is validated, the module transitions to idea generation. Students will engage in creative thinking exercises and structured methodologies to brainstorm a diverse range of potential solutions. Utilising techniques and tools used in innovative idea generation, such as mind tools; customer</p>

journey mapping, Scamper, six thinking hats and other innovation techniques, students will learn to harness their creativity while maintaining strategic focus.

AIMS

This course aims to:

A1	Learn how to observe, research and pinpoint critical issues within a specific context or industry;
A2	Utilise various methods to confirm the problem's importance and impact through data collection, analysis and feedback from relevant stakeholders;
A3	Explore diverse approaches to brainstorm and develop creative solutions, including SWOT analysis, journey mapping, Scamper and other innovative tools;
A4	Familiarise students with techniques for assessing the feasibility and potential impact of generated ideas to select the most promising ones for further development.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

By the end of the course, students will be able to:		Link to Aims
LO1	Recognize and articulate significant problems within a given context or industry;	A1
LO2	Employ various validation techniques, such as stakeholder interviews, surveys, and market analysis, to confirm the importance and relevance of identified problems;	A2
LO3	Apply creative thinking exercises and structured methodologies to brainstorm a diverse range of potential solutions;	A2, A3
LO4	Assess the feasibility, scalability and potential impact of generated ideas using evaluation criteria and cultivate a mindset focused on continuous problem-solving and innovation;	A3, A4

LO5	Use clear and persuasive communication techniques to convey the significance of problems and the potential of proposed solutions.	A4
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TEACHING & LEARNING METHODS	Total Contact Hours: 9
<p>The following Teaching and Learning methods will be employed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Lectures and Presentations</u>: a series of interactive lectures will take place on key concepts, frameworks and methodologies related to problem identification, validation and idea generation. Real-world examples and case studies will be presented to illustrate successful problem identification and idea generation processes • <u>Workshops and Hands-on Activities</u>: a series of workshops, where students have the opportunity to test their ideas, refine the skills acquired during seminars, have hands-on practice on topics already covered and validating problems in a controlled environment. • <u>Group Discussions and Collaborative Learning</u>: Group projects will enable students to work together, to identify problems and generate ideas, fostering teamwork and collaborative problem-solving. • <u>Guest Speakers and Industry Experts</u>: Guest speakers from various industries will share their experiences and insights on problem identification and innovation, providing real-world context and inspiration. Students will have the opportunity to ask questions and engage with industry experts. 	

ASSESSMENT METHODS				
Type #	Students will be assessed by:	Submission Week	% contribution	LOs assessed
C1	Individual Assessment	Week xx	20	1, 4
C2	Group Assessment	Week xx	50	1, 2, 4

C3	Quiz	Week xx	30	1, 4
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FEEDBACK PROVISION

The following methods will be used to provide feedback to students:

Feedback can be understood as any part of the learning process that is designed to guide your progress through your degree programme. We aim to help you reflect on your own learning and help you feel clearer about your progress through clarifying what is expected of you in both formative and summative assessments.

- Summative feedback is feedback on such assessments e.g. the mark given for an exam or a description of how a group of students performed in that exam.
- Formative feedback is feedback given to inform students about their progress, e.g. written feedback on problem sheets or class exercises, comments given as part of a tutorial, seminar or project supervision, etc

OUTLINE OF THE MODULE

UNITS		Topics to be covered
#1	Techniques and tools for innovative idea generation	Opportunity Recognition, Idea Generation & Selection
#2	Validation of identified problems	Creativity Outline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem identification • Problem selection • Divergent thinking • Convergent thinking • The process • Nature of creativity • Myths about creativity • Creativity and the brain • Characteristics of creative individuals • Group creativity Ideation Outline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Idea vs. Opportunity • What are the sources of ideas? • How to generate ideas? • Evaluating ideas

<p>#3</p>	<p>Strategies for identifying market needs and pain points</p>	<p>Innovation Outline</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Basic concepts ● Innovative thinking ● The concept of innovation ● Misconceptions of innovation ● Types and patterns of innovation ● Mapping the innovation space
<p>#4</p>	<p>Types of Innovation</p>	<p><u>Study Questions</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify a creative artist. <p>How is this person different in creativity than you?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Walk from school back to your home and identify ten (10) problems that bothers you on the way. <p>Document it as it will be the base of your ideation process.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select a start up company and determine what sort of problem does it solve with its product or service. <p>Come to class prepared to be able to present to your classmate this one start up company and a list of problems that bothers you.</p> <p><u>Assignment</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Creating your own "Bothers me List". <p>You'll work individually on generating and screening business concepts. Good venture opportunities don't just happen, they emerge from an iterative process of recognition, research, reflection and refinement.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify 10 problems that bothers you in your everyday life. Document it as it will be the base of your ideation process. Problems can be of

		<p>any magnitude, irrespective of your ability of solving them. The main point is that they are problems that you view as a problem.</p> <p>In recording and evaluating your ideas, the screening criteria that you're implicitly using will emerge. It is useful to write these down.</p> <p>2. Using your "Bothers me List" assess the first three (3) most favorite ideas and evaluate them.</p> <p>You are likely to reject many of your ideas very quickly, and so the description of these ideas will be brief. You should spend more time exploring the ideas that pass your (perhaps unconscious) screening criteria. In order to assess them more thoroughly, talk about the most promising ideas with people who know you well, with people who are knowledgeable about the industry, and with potential customers.</p> <p>Finally, you should post a description of your most (one) promising idea and then present your idea in your class (you will have three minutes) that you can get feedback on your most favourite idea from classmates.</p> <p>ii) Conduct an interview with a successful and with a failed entrepreneur. Based on your interviews report on the differences characteristics of the individuals that have contributed to their success and failure.</p> <p>Prepare a five (5) minute presentation (ppt slides) on your findings, and submit a one-page summary of your observations (covering key points from the units taught).</p>
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#5	Guest Speaker (Entrepreneur)	
#6	Conclusions (key take-aways) Reflection & Discussion of assignment - Concluding and Coursework / Assessment Discussion	

ACCESS TO MODULE MATERIAL (Notes, handouts, announcements etc.)

All material used in this module's classes are uploaded in **"academic partner's" e-platform**

RECOMMENDED READING

- [Allen. K. R. \(2020\). Launching New Ventures: An Entrepreneurial Approach. 8th edition, South Western, Cengage Learning.](#)
- [New Venture Creation: Entrepreneurship for the 21st Century](#)
- [Disciplined Entrepreneurship: 24 Steps to a Successful Startup" by Bill Aulet](#)
- [Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. \(2010\). Business Model Generation: A Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.](#)
- [75 Tools for Creative Thinking: A Fun Card Deck for Creative Inspiration](#)

Must read Books:

- [Blue Ocean Strategy](#)
- [Crossing the Chasm](#)
- [Hooked: How to Build Habit-Forming Products](#)
- [The Startup Owner's Manual](#)
- [The Startup Checklist: 25 Steps to a Scalable, High-Growth Business](#)
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- [Testing Business Ideas – Alexander Osterwalder and David Bland](#)
- [Ries, E. \(2011\). The Lean Startup: How Constant Innovation Creates Radically Successful Businesses. London: Portfolio Penguin.](#)
- [Zero Risk Startup: The Ultimate Entrepreneur's Guide to Mitigating Risks When Starting or Growing a Business](#)

- [The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail" by Clayton M. Christensen](#)
- [Venture Deals: Be Smarter Than Your Lawyer and Venture Capitalist.](#)
- [Cowley, P. \(2018\) "The Invested Investor: The new rules for start-ups, scale-ups and angel investing", Invested Investor Limited.](#)
- [Cremades, A. 2016. The art of startup fundraising: pitching investors, negotiating the deal, and everything else entrepreneurs need to know: John Wiley & Sons.](#)

LINKS TO TEACHING MATERIALS

- [Luiss: Slides, Videos \(from Mentoring\), & Tool Problem Validation \(will be finalized by Mid May\)](#)
- [How to evaluate innovative ideas \(6 steps\)](#)
- [The Power of creative constraints \(Video\)](#)
- [Want to be creative? Go for a walk \(Video\)](#)
- [SCAMPER - VIDEO ---- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-OMJINQIZzA>](#)
- [SWOT Analysis - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9-NWhwskTO4>](#)
- [Idea Journals - \[Evernote\]\(<https://evernote.com/>\)](#)
- [\[Notion\]\(<https://www.notion.so/>\)](#)
- [Six Thinking Hats - \[MindTools: Six Thinking Hats\]\(<https://www.mindtools.com/six-thinking-hats>\) - \[De Bono Group: Six Thinking Hats\]\(<https://www.debonogroup.com/services/core-programs/six-thinking-hats/>\)](#)
- [About Miro | Meet the team | Our mission\]\(<https://miro.com/about/>\)](#)
- [Trello - \[Trello\]\(<https://trello.com>\) <http://theleanstartup.com/>](#)
- <https://www.strategyzer.com/books>
- <https://precoil.com/resources/>
- <https://www.boardofinnovation.com/tools/>
- <http://momtestbook.com/>
- <https://designsprintkit.withgoogle.com/>
- <https://getpaidforyourpad.com/blog/the-airbnb-founder-story/>

ADDITIONAL E-BOOKS FROM YOUR ACADEMIC LIBRARY

Please click on the links below to see the lists of eBooks that are available in our Library Catalogue.

- List sources (as well as e-sources) related to the module from your Academic Library

MODULE 2
Solution Development and Validation, Crafting Value Proposition

MODULE CODE	VB6802
MODULE TITLE	Solution Development and Validation, Crafting Value Proposition
PROGRAMME	
DEPARTMENT	
CREDITS	
STAGE OF STUDY	
SEMESTER/SESSION	
LOCATION	
STAFF	
E-MAIL	

DESCRIPTION
<p>This module aims to transition from identifying and generating ideas to developing and validating tangible solutions. This phase is crucial as it bridges the gap between conceptual ideas and practical, implementable solutions that address identified problems effectively. Students will delve into structured methodologies for solution development, ensuring that their ideas are transformed into viable products or services.</p> <p>The module begins with the exploration of various solution development frameworks and techniques, such as value proposition frameworks and individual value propositions. Students will learn how to refine their ideas, create prototypes and iteratively improve their solutions through feedback and A/B testing. Emphasis will be placed on practical application, enabling students to build and refine their solutions in a hands-on, experiential learning environment. A significant component of this module is the validation of solutions. Students will employ various validation techniques to test their solutions, ensuring they meet the needs of the target audience and solve the identified problems effectively. This includes user testing, feedback loops and data-driven validation methods.</p> <p>In addition to developing and validating solutions, students will learn to craft compelling value propositions. This involves articulating the unique benefits and value their solution offers to customers and stakeholders. Students will explore techniques for effectively communicating the value proposition, prototyping techniques for MVP's ensuring it resonates with the target audience and differentiates their solution in the marketplace.</p>

AIMS	
This module aims to:	
A1	Equip students with the skills to design and develop effective and innovative solutions to complex problems, ensuring that these solutions address identified needs and opportunities.

A2	Teach students methods to rigorously test and validate their solutions through user feedback, prototyping and iterative refinement to ensure feasibility and effectiveness in real-world applications.
A3	Enable students to articulate clear, compelling and competitive value propositions for their solutions that highlight unique benefits and address customer pain points effectively.
A4	Foster an understanding of how to integrate perspectives from various disciplines (such as marketing, finance, engineering, and design) to create holistic and sustainable solutions and value propositions.
A5	Prepare students to strategically plan the introduction of their solutions to the market, considering factors like market needs, competitive landscape, and go-to-market strategies to maximize impact and adoption.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

By the end of the unit, a student will be able to:		Link to aims
LO1	Demonstrate the ability to analyse complex problems and identify key needs and opportunities for innovative solutions.	A1
LO2	Utilise various validation techniques, such as prototyping and A/B testing, to gather and analyze feedback on proposed solutions.	A1, A2
LO3	Formulate clear and compelling value propositions that effectively communicate the unique benefits of the solution.	A3
LO4	Collaborate with peers from diverse disciplines to incorporate different perspectives and expertise into the solution development process.	A4
LO5	Be able develop a strategic plan for the market launch of the solution, including positioning, marketing strategies, and Go-to-Market tactics.	A5

TEACHING & LEARNING METHODS

Total Contact Hours: 7

The following teaching & learning methods will be employed:

- Lectures and Interactive Seminars: Deliver foundational knowledge and key concepts through lectures, complemented by interactive seminars that encourage discussion, questioning and deeper exploration of topics. This will help to provide a theoretical understanding and facilitate critical thinking and engagement with the material.
- Case Studies and Real-world Examples: Analyse and discuss case studies and real-world examples to illustrate successful and unsuccessful solution development, validation and value proposition crafting. This will help students understand practical applications of theoretical concepts and learn from existing business scenarios.
- Workshops and Group projects: Conduct workshops and practical sessions where students can engage in activities such as brainstorming, prototyping, and creating value propositions. Group projects will enhance collaboration, communication and the ability to integrate cross-functional perspectives in a team setting.
- Field Visits and Industry Placements: Arrange visits to companies or industry placements where students can observe and engage with professionals working on solution

development and validation. This will give the opportunity to the students to have a real-world exposure and practical experience in a professional setting.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Type #	Students will be assessed by:	Submission Week	% contribution	LOs assessed
C1	Individual Assessment	Week xx	30%	
C2	Group Assessment	Week xx	50%	
C3	Quiz	Week xx	20%	

FEEDBACK PROVISION

The following methods will be used to provide feedback to students:

Feedback can be understood as any part of the learning process that is designed to guide your progress through your degree programme. We aim to help you reflect on your own learning and help you feel clearer about your progress through clarifying what is expected of you in both formative and summative assessments.

- Summative feedback is feedback on such assessments, e.g., the mark given for an exam or a description of how a group of students performed in that exam.
- Formative feedback is feedback given to inform students about their progress, e.g., written feedback on problem sheets or class exercises, comments given as part of a tutorial, seminar or project supervision, etc.

OUTLINE OF THE MODULE

UNITS		Topics to be covered
#1	Solution validation methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design thinking tools for exploring and validating solutions • A/B testing, usability testing, and pilot studies • Assess solution viability and market readiness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Introduction to Design Thinking * Understanding User Needs (Empathy Maps) * Setting up A/B test: hypotheses, variables, and metrics
#2	Crafting a unique value proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding Customer Needs and Differentiation Strategies • Utilising the Value Proposition Canvas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Planning Usability Tests and pilot Studies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presenting individual value propositions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market readiness (market analysis, competitive analysis) Assumption Validation (desirability, feasibility, visibility) Assumption Mapping, Experimentation, Business Model Reviews, Pivoting Define Minimum Viable Business Product (MVBP) Minimum Viable Business Product Examples Validate the hypothesis and reflections - The Mom test
#3	<p>Prototyping techniques for MVPs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating the minimum viable products <p>Gathering feedback from users</p>	<p>Assignment</p> <p>Pick your favourite idea that you developed in the previous module and use the "Test and Learning Card" to fill up the following items:</p> <p>TEST and LEARNING CARD</p> <p>Test Name: XXXXX</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> We believe that... (hypothesis): To validate that we will... (action): Our belief is right if... (metric) From the test, we found out & learnt that... (result); Therefore, we will... (conclusion)
#4		
Guest Speaker		
#5	Conclusions (key take-aways)	Reflection & Discussion of assignment

		- Concluding and Coursework / Assessment Discussion
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ACCESS TO MODULE MATERIAL (Notes, handouts, announcements etc.)

All materials used in this module's classes are uploaded on **"academic partner's" e-platform**

RECOMMENDED READING

- [Allen. K. R. \(2020\). Launching New Ventures: An Entrepreneurial Approach. 8th-edition, South Western, Cengage Learning.](#)
- [New Venture Creation: Entrepreneurship for the 21st Century](#)
- [Disciplined Entrepreneurship: 24 Steps to a Successful Startup" by Bill Aulet](#)
- [Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. \(2010\). Business Model Generation: A Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.](#)
- [Value Proposition Design: How to Create Products and Services Customers Want" by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur](#)
- [Ries, E. \(2011\). The Lean Startup: How Constant Innovation Creates Radically Successful Businesses. London: Portfolio Penguin.](#)
- [Fitzpatrick, Rob: The mom test – How to talk to customers](#)
- [This Is Service Design Thinking: Basics, Tools, Cases" by Marc Stickdorn and Jakob Schneider](#)

Must read Books:

- o [Blue Ocean Strategy](#)
- o [Crossing the Chasm](#)
- o [Hooked: How to Build Habit-Forming Products](#)
- o [The Startup Owner's Manual](#)
- o [The Startup Checklist: 25 Steps to a Scalable, High-Growth Business](#)
- o [The Four Steps to the Epiphany](#)
- o [The Startup Owners Manual](#)
- o [Zero to One: Notes on Start Ups, or How to Build the Future](#)
- o [Zero Risk Startup: The Ultimate Entrepreneur's Guide to Mitigating Risks When Starting or Growing a Business](#)
- o [Venture Deals: Be Smarter Than Your Lawyer and Venture Capitalist.](#)
- o [Cowley, P. \(2018\) "The Invested Investor: The new rules for start-ups, scale-ups and angel investing", Invested Investor Limited.Cremades, A. 2016. The art of startup fundraising: pitching investors, negotiating the deal, and everything else entrepreneurs need to know: John Wiley & Sons.](#)

IDEO Design Kit:

Human-Centered Design Toolkit: [IDEO Design Kit](#)

[Methods: IDEO Methods](#)

Strategyzer Blog and Resources:

[Value Proposition Design](#)

[Testing Business Ideas: Strategyzer Resources](#)

LINKS TO TEACHING MATERIALS

All material used in this module's classes are available in electronic form through G classroom or the through the academic partners e-platform.

[Luiss: Slides, Videos \(from Mentoring\), & Tool Solution Validation \(will be finalized by Mid May\)](#)

- [UTH Tim Heiler- Instant Innovation Cards](#)
- [UTH \(in Greek needs translation\)](#)
- [FEA: Slides \(from Mentoring\)](#)
- [UTH Updated Empathy Map Canvas](#)
- UTH(in Greek needs translation)

YouTube Videos:

- IDEO: Design Thinking: [IDEO Design Thinking Video](#)
- What is a Value Proposition? (Strategyzer): [Strategyzer Video](#)
- The Lean Startup: Eric Ries: [Lean Startup Video](#)

ADDITIONAL E-BOOKS FROM YOUR ACADEMIC LIBRARY

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MODULE 3

Market Discovery

MODULE CODE	VB6803
MODULE TITLE	Market Discovery
PROGRAMME	
DEPARTMENT	
CREDITS	
STAGE OF STUDY	
SEMESTER/SESSION	
LOCATION	
STAFF	
E-MAIL	

DESCRIPTION
<p>The module is an in-depth exploration of market research principles, designed to equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to understand and analyse market dynamics. This module encompasses a wide range of topics, including market segmentation, target market identification, competitive analysis, consumer behaviour, and market trends. Through a blend of theoretical frameworks and practical applications, students will learn how to gather, interpret, and utilise market data to make informed business decisions.</p> <p>The primary aim of the Market Discovery module is to empower students with the capability to understand market structures and to gain a comprehensive understanding of different market types, structures, and dynamics. The students will gain fruitful insights on how to conduct market research and develop proficiency in both qualitative and quantitative research methods to gather relevant market data and how to interpret data and insights to identify market opportunities and threats.</p> <p>Moreover, throughout the module, the students will acquire knowledge on how to segment markets, evaluate consumer behaviour, perform competitive analysis, identify market trends, and develop market strategies. By the end of this module, students will be adept at utilising market research tools and techniques to uncover valuable insights, enabling them to contribute effectively to the strategic planning and decision-making processes within any business environment.</p>

AIMS	
This module aims to:	
A1	Equip students with a deep understanding of different market structures, types, and the forces that drive market behaviour and changes.
A2	Develop students' ability to employ both qualitative and quantitative research methods to collect and analyze market data effectively.
A3	Teach students to segment markets accurately, identify target audiences, and understand consumer behavior to tailor marketing strategies effectively.

A4	Enable students to synthesise market research findings into actionable business strategies, helping organisations capitalise on market opportunities and navigate potential challenges.
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LEARNING OUTCOMES

By the end of the unit, a student will be able to:		Link to aims
LO1	Analyse the factors that influence market behaviour and the forces driving market changes.	A1
LO2	Utilise appropriate data collection methods and tools to gather relevant market information and interpret market data using statistical and analytical techniques.	A2
LO3	Identify and evaluate target market segments based on demographic, psychographic, and behavioural characteristics.	A3
LO4	Develop strategic marketing plans that align with business goals and market opportunities.	A4
LO5	Present and justify marketing strategies and decisions based on comprehensive market analysis.	A4

TEACHING & LEARNING METHODS

Total Contact Hours: 10

The following teaching & learning methods will be employed:

- Lectures: Provide foundational knowledge and theoretical frameworks related to market dynamics, research techniques, market segmentation, consumer behaviour, and strategic planning.
- Case Studies and Real-World Examples: Analyse and discuss case studies and real-world examples to illustrate successful and unsuccessful solution development, validation, and value proposition crafting. This will help students understand practical applications of theoretical concepts and learn from existing business scenarios.
- Workshops and Group Projects: Conduct workshops and practical sessions where students can engage in activities such as brainstorming, prototyping, and creating value propositions. Group projects will enhance collaboration, communication, and the ability to integrate cross-functional perspectives in a team setting.
- Field Visits and Industry Placements: Arrange visits to companies or industry placements where students can observe and engage with professionals working on solution development and validation. This will give the students the opportunity to gain real-world exposure and practical experience in a professional setting.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Type #	Students will be assessed by:	Submission Week	% contribution	LOs Assessed
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C1	Individual Assessment	Week xx	30%	
C2	Group Assessment	Week xx	50%	
C3	Quiz	Week xx	20%	LO 1,2,3,4,5

FEEDBACK PROVISION

The following methods will be used to provide feedback to students:

Feedback can be understood as any part of the learning process that is designed to guide your progress through your degree programme. We aim to help you reflect on your own learning and help you feel clearer about your progress through clarifying what is expected of you in both formative and summative assessments.

- Summative feedback is feedback on such assessments, e.g., the mark given for an exam or a description of how a group of students performed in that exam.
- Formative feedback is feedback given to inform students about their progress, e.g., written feedback on problem sheets or class exercises, comments given as part of a tutorial, seminar, or project supervision.

OUTLINE OF THE MODULE

UNITS		Topics to be covered
#1	Fundamentals of market research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding customer segmentation for targeted strategies • Analysis of the target market for effective positioning 	<u>Fundamentals of Market Research</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Market research process: (why is market research critical for startups?) ▪ Risk mitigation: identifying the main market risks: demand, market size & growth, competition risk, economic risk, pricing risk, and international & geopolitical risk ▪ Types of segmentation ▪ Creating customer personas ▪ Market size and growth (TAM, SAM, SOM) ▪ Competitive analysis <u>Utilisation of Digital Tools</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Online surveys and polls ▪ Web analytics and social media analytics
#2	Utilisation of digital tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods for data collection, analysis, and visualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data analysis and visualisation tools ▪ Customer relationship management (CRM) tools

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing tools to enhance market insights and decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competitor analysis tools SEO and SEM tools <p><u>Hands-on Projects and Case Studies</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing a market research plan Conducting an online customer feedback survey Web analytics and social media campaign analysis SEO strategy development CRM system utilisation Creating a data-driven presentation (using free data visualisation tools) to summarise the findings from the market research.
#3	<p>Hands-on projects and case studies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applying market research techniques to real-world scenarios Developing skills through practical exercises and simulations 	
#4	<p>Conclusions (key takeaways)</p>	<p>Reflection & Discussion of the Assignment</p> <p>Conclusion and Coursework/Assessment Discussion</p>

ACCESS TO MODULE MATERIAL (Notes, handouts, announcements etc.)

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RECOMMENDED READING

Books:

- [Allen. K. R. \(2020\). Launching New Ventures: An Entrepreneurial Approach. 8th-edition, South Western, Cengage Learning.](#)
- [New Venture Creation: Entrepreneurship for the 21st Century](#)
- [Disciplined Entrepreneurship: 24 Steps to a Successful Startup" by Bill Aulet](#)
- [Continuous Discovery Habits: Discover Products that Create Customer Value and Business Value](#)
- [Digital Marketing: A Practical Approach](#)

Must read Books:

- o [Blue Ocean Strategy](#)
- o [Crossing the Chasm](#)
- o [Hooked: How to Build Habit-Forming Products](#)
- o [The Startup Owner's Manual](#)
- o [The Startup Checklist: 25 Steps to a Scalable, High-Growth Business](#)
- o [The Four Steps to the Epiphany](#)

- o [The Startup Owners Manual](#)
- o [Zero to One: Notes on Start Ups, or How to Build the Future](#)
- o [Fitzpatrick, Rob: The mom test – How to talk to customers](#)
- o [Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. \(2010\). Business Model Generation: A Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers, Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.](#)
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- o [Venture Deals: Be Smarter Than Your Lawyer and Venture Capitalist.](#)
- o [Cowley, P. \(2018\) "The Invested Investor: The new rules for start-ups, scale-ups and angel investing", Invested Investor Limited.](#)
- o [Cremades, A. 2016. The art of startup fundraising: pitching investors, negotiating the deal, and everything else entrepreneurs need to know: John Wiley & Sons.](#)

LINKS TO TEACHING MATERIALS

All material used in this module's classes are available in electronic form through G classroom or the through the academic partners e-platform.

- UTH [Research on B2B Marketing Ideation: Stats, Insights, Data](#)
- UTH(in Greek needs translation)
- UTH [Disciplined Entrepreneurship Startup Tactics - Market Research](#)
- UTH [The Market Opportunity Navigator](#)
- UTH [Dot Voting](#)
- UTH [ArangoDB Case Studies](#)
- UTH [Polarity Approach to Continuity and Transformation](#)

YouTube Videos:

- [An Introduction to Market Segmentation](#)

- [Quantitative vs. Qualitative Research: The Differences Explained](#)
- [Understanding consumer behaviour, from the inside out](#)
- [What is Consumer Behavior? \(With Real World Examples\)](#)
- [Neuromarketing: How brands are getting your brain to buy more stuff](#)

Additional e-Books from your Academic Library

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- List sources (as well as e-sources) related to the module from your Academic Library